

Trends of Geography Education in Nepal

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Abstract: This study appraises Trends of Geography Education in Nepal by applying library based method. This paper found that Trends of Geography Education, studies interactive relationship between human being and environment is an oldest subject studied globally In the case of Nepal, it is formally applied by Durbar High School first in 1834 AD. Later wards, with establishment of School Leaving Certificate board in 1990, geography education became 100 marks 'as a compulsory subject in school education. In the course of curricular practice, National Education System Plan (NESP) re/structured this in to limited 50 marks' compulsory subject in 2028 but NESP revised and implemented curriculum implemented plan 2038. After that geography subject was included in compulsory social studies subject. Accordingly, National Education Curricula, 2049 and Secondary Education Curriculum (SEC) 2076 also included geography subject in social studies and optional subject. Presently SEC has developed two streams (i.e general & vocational) curriculum at secondary level. Despite tremendous importance of geography subject in school curricula, un/knowingly the school education system has been giving remarkably poor importance in school curricula of Nepal. The number of students interested in geography subjects is decreasing annually thus suggested to re/structure geography education according to changing time contexts. Better to include geography subject by local governments having different geographic features and suggested to offer Geographical Information System (GIS) program in school level for mounting its popularity in this modern technological era.

Key Words: Geography education, curriculum structure, social studies, historical development, geographic information system.

I. Introduction

Geography is a branch of academic study broadly concerned with the Earth. Geographers can be roughly divided into those concerned with physical earth processes (physical geography), such as erosion and sedimentation, and those who are more concerned with human activities (human geography). Geography is a basic subject for all human beings to learn. It is an essential academic field for all walks of life. By definition, Geography is the study of locational and spatial variation in both physical and human phenomena on earth. Similarly, Geography is the study of places, people, and the natural and built environments they occupy. The meaning of geography education has derived from the interrelationship between two academic domains are geography and education. It becomes a subfield of geography (Bednarz, 2010). Geography education has become a more important subfield of geography in the United States despite its different nature from other disciplinary subfields and observed status (Bednarz, 2014). The literal meaning of geography is to describe the earth, while education refers to the process of receiving or giving systematic instruction. Education is the fundamental process of reproduction of a discipline. Geography education is the study of spatial variations in the provision, take-up, quality of, and outputs from educational facilities and resources for the instruction in the schools and universities (Gregory, 2009 p. 186). It covers complex concepts understood by explaining its relationship to the discipline of geography, detailing its aims and place in formal and non-formal education, and considering its essential components, such as subject matter, skills, and perspectives (Gerber, 1990 p. 6).

Today's conception of geographical education is influenced by four main parameters which also serve as reference frames. 1) The values which are expressed by the general aims of a school system which find expression in the aims assigned to be taught in geography by the educational institutions; 2) the conception of geographical knowledge; 3) the conception of learning; 4) and the epistemology of the discipline (Hertig&Varcher, 2004).

It shows that the geography education combined new multidisciplinary, new knowledge boundaries, and better access to knowledge through information technology. This subject has further heightened the interdisciplinary competitive knowledge for obtaining academic and practical knowledge of developing countries like Nepal. Geography education is the oldest academic discipline at the school level and university level in Nepal. The history of geography as an educational field of study dates back to the beginning of the 20th century in Nepal. However, the use of geographic thoughts, concepts, and geographical descriptions of the place go to the Vedic period (Subedi&Poudel, 2005). For the first time, JayPrithiviBahadur Singh was introduced to geography subject in 1901 at the school-level curriculum. Then, geography developed as an organized subject after the establishment the School Leaving Certificate examination for Durbar School used to be conducted by the University of Calcutta, India up until the Nepal SLC Board was founded in 1934 enhanced the popularity of this discipline at the school level (Khatriwada, 2019; Adhikari, 2010). Nevertheless, in the early days, school and university-level geography curriculum seemed to be guided by University of Calcutta, India curriculum in Nepal. NESP 1971 implemented the Geography subject as a compulsory subject and limited to 50 marks. NESP 1971 implemented the Geography subject as a compulsory subject and limited to 50 marks. However, sometimes geography subject was implemented as compulsory and optional subject. At present time, geography is taught in Nepal as an elective subject from the secondary level to higher education, and geography education is included as a part of compulsory social studies at the secondary level. The geography education was marginalized as one of the subjects in the least favored optional category, and the provision competed with mathematics and science (Subedi& Joshi, 1997). Therefore, there is a lack of geography subject in the school curriculum. Thus, it is mandatory for everyone to take initiative from all places to increase the interest of the talented/ genuine students towards the subject of geography.

II. Method and Materials

The research methodology is the process of doing research. Kitchen and Tate (2000) observes that it is a coherent set of rules and procedures which can be used to investigate or way for solve the problem. This paper based on the reviews of secondary sources of data. Data were collected from different journals, books and e-resources for this paper. The published and unpublished documents of the Curriculum Development Center (CDC), the reports of the High-Level Education Commission and National Education Commission reports of the various donor agencies, and Periodic Plans were sources of information. The data of student numbers were collected from the official records of the National Examination Board, Bhaktapur.

III. Result and Discussion

One of the outstanding features of recent educational developments has been the rise of the geography as a well-established discipline in school to university level. The number of professional chairs of geography in this country and in the common-wealth has steadily increased, so much so that all except one of the Universities of the United Kingdom now has at least one professorship in geography.

Geography intersects with education's teacher preparation domain, research may explore how teachers gain the specific kinds of subject matter knowledge needed to teach and the competence required to explain concepts and to teach fundamental geographic skills. Geography questions addressed within this shared geography education dominion might be included such types of Questions 'How do teachers-to-be construct their understanding of the fundamentals of geography? What constitutes good geography teaching and how can teachers and administrators be trained to discern and foster quality instruction once it is identified?' Geography education

research is where research in geography and in education overlap. Imagine geography and education to be rotating overlapping discs. The overlapping of geography education is presented in fig.1

Figure1 Geography Education defined as the overlap between Geography and Education
Developed by Authors

Historical perspectives of Geography Education: From the ancient period indirectly the geography education were teaching in Nepal but Geography education were formally starting from the establishment of the Durbar High School in 1854 A.D. by Junga Bahadur Rana. Jaya Prithvi Bahadur Singh is credited for this initiative at the school level in Nepal. The curriculum was primarily based on British (Indian) system since all the instructors were trained in India and the subject mainly focused on physical geography. Texts and supplementary materials were largely based on the Indian experience and were in English (Subedi, 2013).

The school was originally built to teach sons of Ranas exclusively but was opened to public citizens in 1901 by Dev Shamsher Jang Bahadur Rana. After the establishment of SLC board in Nepal in 1934, it included as a compulsory subject carrying out 100 marks and the Nepali context was added to the geography curriculum and this provision continued till 1950. The government of Nepal revised the school level curriculum after 1950 and there were some changes. After that the geography subject became an optional subject including history subject. Students were given the opportunity required to choose either Geography or History in their secondary level education. When managing the optional subject to the Geography subject in the curriculum after that gradually decreasing the importance of this subject.

National Education System Plan (NESP): NESP 1971 launched Geography was included as part of social studies and optional subject. There were three levels of the school level i.e. presented in table. 1:

Table 1: Primary Level curriculum (Class I- III)

S. N.	Subjects	School Hours (%)	Full Marks
1	Nepali Language	40	300
2	Arithmetic	30	200
3	Social Studies	20	100
4	Physical Education, Personal Hygiene and Handicrafts and Drawing	10	50
	Total	100	650

खनाल, अधिकारी, कोइराला, रलामीछाने, २०७५

Table 1 presented the curriculum of the primary level class I to III. There are four subjects and full marks 650. Only 100 full marks of social studies out of 650 total full marks. Part of the geography subject also included in social studies.

Table 2: Lower Secondary Level curriculum (Class IV-VII)

S. N.	Subjects	% School Hours	Full Marks
1	Nepali Language	30	200
2	Nepali Language (class VI and VII)	25	170
3	Elementary Sanskrit (Classes VI & VII)	5	30
4	One of the UN Languages	10	100
5	Social Studies	13	100
6	Mathematics	20	150
7	Science	10	100
8	Pre-Vocational Training	10	100
9	Physical Education & Hygiene	7	50
	Total	130	1000

खनाल, अधिकारी, कोइराला, रलामीछाने, २०७५

Table 2. Show curriculum of the primary level class IV to VIII. There are nine subjects and full marks 1000. Only 100 full marks of social studies out of 1000 total in full marks. Part of the geography subject also included in social studies.

Table 3: General Secondary Schools curriculum (VIII to X)

S. N.	Subjects	% School Hours	Full Marks
1	Nepali Language	12	100
2	One of the UN Languages	12	100
3	Mathematics	12	100
4	History and Geography	12	100
5	Health Education	5	50
6	Panchayat	5	50
7	Science	12	100
8	One of the Vocational Subjects	20	200
9	Optional Subject	10	100
	Total	100	900

खनाल, अधिकारी, कोइराला, रलामीछाने, २०७५

Table 3. show the school level curriculum of Nepal Education System Plan 1971- 75. In this plan the geography subject included the social studies discipline in primary and secondary level. Similarly, the geography discipline

was included in secondary level of the 50 full marks out of 900 full marks. This is the right stage to emphasis the making education vocation-oriented and socially useful. The plan focuses the appropriate Classroom teaching will, therefore, lay stress on the lives of national heroes and the contribution of the Royal Family to the development and enhancement of the country. Extra-curricular activities will be designed to foster patriotism, loyalty, and sense of discipline, appropriate motivation and right skills. This level will place special emphasis on forming habits of self-reliance, responsibility, honesty and co-operation. An attempt should be made at this stage to inculcate love and respect for labor. Teachers should lay-out a plan for engaging the students in some useful work like woodcraft, stationery work and farming (Paudel, 2017).

Curriculum Implementation Plan 1982: The NESP was revised the curriculum and implemented the Curriculum Implementation Plan in 1982. It was offered the geography as an optional subject in secondary schools. The commission implemented the compulsory social studies subject. Geography also included in the social studies the social studies curriculum in school level. The geography discipline included the as a part in the compulsory social studies.

Table 4: Draft of curriculum of Primary and Lower secondary level (I-VII)

S.N.	Subject	Class 1-3	Class 4-5	Class 6-7
1	Nepali	300	150	120
2	Mathematics	200	100	100
3	Social	100	100	100
4	Physical Education , sanitation, Paintings and Handicrafts	50	-	-
5	Sanskrit		50	30
6	English		100	100
7	Physical Education		50	50
8	Science and Health		70+30	80+20
9	Moral Education		50	50
10	Pre-vocational Education		-	50
Total		650	700	700

खनाल, अधिकारी, कोइराला, रलामीछाने, २०७५

Table 4 has Shown the primary and lower secondary level curriculum of the curriculum implementation plan 1982. The curriculum was implemented in four subjects in grades 1-3. In social studies, out of total 650 full marks, there were only 100 full marks. The part of basic knowledge of geography was included in the compulsory social studies. Primary and Lower secondary level applied the class 4 – 7. There are eight subjects and 100 full marks of social studies out of 700 full marks. The geography parts were included in compulsory social studies.

Table 5 :Draft of curriculum of Secondary level (Class 8-10)

S.N.	Subjects	Class-8	Class 9-10
1	Nepali	100	100
2	English	100	100
3	Mathematics	100	100
4	Vocational subject any one	100	100
5	History	75	-
6	Geography	75	-
7	Panchayat or Civic life, Science+ Health	50 80+20	-
Optional I			100

Optional II			100
Additional Optional			100
Total		700	700

खनाल, अधिकारी, कोइराला, रलामीछाने, २०७५

Table 5. Show secondary level curriculum of the curriculum implementation plan. The curriculum implemented the seven subjects in class 8. The total marks for geography education was only 75 marks out of 700. Similarly, the curriculum implemented the seven subjects in class 9 -10 and full marks 700. Geography was not included as the compulsory subject in classes 9-10. The curriculum places geography subject an optional subject.

National Education Commission 2049: The curriculum was revised of 2038 in 2049 because democracy was restored in Nepal in 2046 BS and National Education Commission was formed in 2047 BS. According to that commission provide education of the international standards and submitted the report in 2049 BS. The Commission implemented that the three level of education in Nepal. There were primary level and lower secondary level respectively class 1- 5 and class 6-8. Geography education was included in the compulsory subject as a part of social education in primary and secondary level education. The primary school level education has presented in table 6:

Table 6. Subject for Primary School Level (1 to 5)

Subjects	Class				
	1	2	3	4	5
Nepali Language	100	100	100	100	100
Mother Language and other Language	100	100	100	100	100
English Language	-	-	-	100	100
Mathematics	100	100	100	100	100
Social Education	100	100	100	100	100
Health, Physical and Environment Education	50	50	50	50	50
Arts	50	50	50	50	50
Science	-	-	-	100	100
Total	500	500	500	700	700

CDC, 2016

Table 6 has shown the primary school level curriculum of the Nepal Education Commission 2049. The curriculum implemented the six subjects in class 1-3. Only 100 full marks of social education out of 500 total full marks. Basic knowledge of geography was included in compulsory social education. Similarly, the curriculum implemented the Eight subjects in class 4-5 and 100 full marks out of 700 total marks. There were not included the compulsory subject of geography. The geography part was included in compulsory social education.

Table 7: Curriculum for Lower Secondary Level (Class, 6-8)

Subjects	6	7	8
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Nepali	100	100	100
Sanskrit	50	50	50
English	100	100	100
Mathematics	100	100	100
Science	100	100	100
Social Education	100	100	100
Health and Physical Education	50	50	50
Optional Language	100	100	100
Arts/ Pre-vocational education	50	50	50
Total	750	750	750

CDC, 2016

Table 7 has shown the lower secondary school level curriculum of the Nepal Education Commission 2049. The curriculum implemented nine subjects in grades 6-8. Social Studies had only 100 full marks out of a total of 750 full marks. Geography was not included as a compulsory subject. Geography was included in compulsory social education.

Table 8: Curriculum for secondary Level (Class, 9-10)

Subjects	Class -9	Class -10
Nepali	100	100
English	100	100
Mathematics	100	100
Science	100	100
Social Education	100	100
Optional	200	200
Additional optional	100	100
Total	800	800

CDC, 2016

Table 8 presented the Secondary School Level education of the Nepal Education Commission 2049. The education has implemented the eight subjects in class 9-10. Only 100 full marks of social education out of 800 totals of full marks. There was not included the compulsory subject of geography. The geography was included as a part of compulsory social education.

The secondary curriculum level were included the Eight subjects and geography was included as a part of compulsory social education. Annual hours and percentage of the different units of social education has presented in table 9.

Table 9: Social studies for General secondary Schools (IX to X)

S. N.	Unit Details	Annual hours	Percentage
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			(%)
1	We and our society	15	8.8
2	Development and development infrastructure	16	9.4
3	Our tradition, social values and norms	16	9.4
4	Social problems and solutions	19	11.2
5	Civic sense	22	12.9
6	Our earth	27	15.9
7	Our past	22	12.9
8	Economic activities	18	10.6
9	Our international relationship and co-operations	15	8.8
Total		170	100

CDC, 2016

Table 9: has shown the secondary level subject of NEC 2049. The geography subject matter was included in compulsory social studies in unit 6 (earth). The geography subject matter has not detail knowledge only provide the generally knowledge to the student. The curriculum introduced the New subject Population and environment and replaced the geography subject as a compulsory subject and placed the optional subject geography. In 2055 higher level of Education commission suggested the two level of school education. It was primary class 1- 5 and secondary level class 6-12. Secondary level education also was divided into three parts. They were the lower secondary class 6-8, secondary level class 9-10, and higher secondary level class 11-12. The approval for this Primary Education Curriculum was submitted in 2060 BS after the incorporation of suggestions and recommendations of the 'High Level Working Committee on Education, 2058 BS,' 'Impact Study of Primary Curriculum, 2059 BS. In 2057 New curriculum of Higher Secondary (10+2) Education implemented Geography subject as one of the optional subjects with 100 full marks (75% theory and 25% practical) in the higher secondary level curriculum. National Curriculum Framework (for School Education in Nepal, 2063 (Modified, 2071) recommended two levels of secondary level. They are basic level education class 1- 8 and secondary education level class 9- 12. It was also suggested the compulsory subject of social studies in basic education level and secondary education. Geography subject was included in social studies.

The government of Nepal implemented the School Sector Reform Program (SSRP) in 2009-15.A.D. The objectives of this programme are to improve and increase access to quality basic education for children from marginalized groups. The program emphasizes increasing the relevance of school education, the Plan intends to restructure the current school system forming a coherent and integrated school structure system of 1-8 basic level education and 9-12 secondary level education has gained momentum across the social and political domains. The program intends to Structural integration of existing schools into their nearest stages are 1-3, 1-5, and 1-8 at the basic education level and 9-10, and 11-12 at the secondary education level. (Nepal, 2009). The School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP, 2066-72) is based on the Education for all (2009-15) National Action Plan and the three-year plan.

The period of SSRP was expired and the political transformation and constitution of Nepal brought about the geographical restructuring and establishment the federal system under the 2015 promulgated constitution (constituent Assembly Secretariat (CAS), 2015). To address the federal system of the country, modifying the SSRP and the Government of Nepal implemented the School Sector Development Project (SSDP) in 2016. A strong school education system, which preserve the achievements made over the past years and the ensures minimum quality and accessibility while allowing adaptation to the diverse context and needs within the country is crucial for progress towards the SDGs and for building a democratic federal republic under the new constitution.

National Education Curriculum, 2076: According to the slogan of prosperous Nepal, happy Nepali and the line with Nepal's international commitments and the spirit of Nepal's constitution, the school sector development project (2016-23) has accepted education from class 1 to 8 as basic level education. Similarly, secondary level class 9 to 12 has been accepted. Nepali uniqueness, useful values of Nepal's fundamental

philosophy, the global concept of education, the guarantee of a society-oriented inclusive democracy will be the philosophical foundation of Nepal (Commission, 2075). As suggested by this commission Secondary Education Curriculum- 2076 implemented the academic year 2077/ 78 in class 11 and implemented in 2078/79 at class 12.

National Education Curriculum, 2076: General Section

Table 10: Basic Education curriculum (Class 1-3)

S.N.	Subjects	Credit hours	Working Hours
1	Nepali	5	160
2	English	4	128
3	Mathematics	4	128
4	Science , Health and Physical Education	4	128
5	Social Studies	4	128
6	Mother language/ Local subject matter	5	160
Total		26	832

स्रोत: पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६

Table 10 has shown the basic education School Level curriculum of the National Education Commission 2076. The curriculum implemented the six subjects in class 1-3. Only 4 credit hours out of 26 full credit hours of social education. Similarly, time allocated the 128 working hours and out of 832 total working hours. Subject matter of geography subject was included in compulsory social studies.

Table 11. Basic Education (Class 4-6)

S.N.	Subjects	Credit hours	Working hours
1	Nepali	5	160
2	English	5	160
3	Mathematics	5	160
4	Science and Technology	5	160
5	Social Studies or Human value Education	5	160
6	Health, Physical or Creative art	3	96
7	Mother language/ Local subject	4	128
Total		32	1024

(पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६)

Table 11 has shown the basic education School Level curriculum of the National Education Commission 2076. The curriculum implemented the seven subjects in class 4-6. Only 5 credit hours out of 32 full credit hours of social education. Similarly, time was allocated the 160 working hours and out of 1024 total working hours. Subject matter of geography was included in compulsory social studies.

Table 12: Basic Education level (Class 6-8)

S.N.	Subjects	Credit hours	Working hours
1	Nepali	5	160
2	English	5	160
3	Mathematics	5	160
4	Science and Technology	5	160
5	Social Studies or Human value Education	5	160
6	Health, Physical or Creative art	3	96
7	Mother language/ Local subject	4	128
Total		32	1024

पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६

Table 12 presented the basic education level School Level curriculum of the National Education Commission 2076. The curriculum implemented the seven subjects in class 6-8. Only 5 credit hours out of 32 full credit hours of social education. Similarly, time allocated the 160 working hours and out of 1024 total working hours. Subject matter of geography subject was included in compulsory social studies.

Table 13: Secondary Education (Class 9-10)

S. N.	Subjects	Credit Hour	Working Hour
1	Nepali	5	160
2	English	5	160
3	Mathematics	5	160
4	Science and Technology	5	160
5	Social Studies	4	128
6	Optional I	4	128
7	Optional II	4	128
	Total	32	1024

पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६

Table 13 presented the secondary education level of class 9 and 10. There are five compulsory subjects out of seven subjects. Subject matter of Geography was included in social studies and Geography subject was included in optional. A credit hour for Social studies is 4 out of 32 credit hours. Similarly, 128 working hours it is implemented out of a total of 1024 working hours. Table 14: Secondary Education (Class 11-12)

S. N.	Subject	Credit Hour (Class 11)	Credit Hour (Class 12)
1	Nepali	3	3
2	English	4	4
3	Social studies	5	-
4	Life skill	-	5
5	Optional I	5	5
6	Optional II	5	5
7	Total	27	27
8	Optional Additional	5	5
Total		54	54

पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६

Table 14 presented the secondary education level 11 and 12. Subject matter of the Geography subject included in compulsory social studies. It has allocated 15 percentage (%) and 18 working hours out of 160 hours. The

subject matter of Geography subject included in compulsory social studies. Geography subject included the optional II in class 11 and 12 and allocated the time 5 credit hour and 160 working hour.

Table 15: *Social studies for General secondary Schools (Class -11)*

S.N.	Units details	Working hours	Percentage (%)
1	Introduction to social studies and method	8	6.7
2	Development and Evolution of human or society	9	7.5
3	Geography and social relationship	18	15
4	Historical Development of Nepal and World	14	11.7
5	Social identity, diversity and class division	15	12.5
6	Citizen Awareness and the Constitution	13	10.8
7	Settlement, urbanization, migration and population	13	10.8
8	Education and Health	10	8.4
9	Economic and development	13	10.8
10	International relation and current events of Nepal	7	5.8
Total		120	100

पाठ्यक्रम, २०७६

Table 15. Show the social studies subject of secondary education level class 11. Part of the geography subject matter included in compulsory social studies as a topic of geography and social relationship. It has allocated 15 percentage (%) and 18 working hours out of 120 of the geography and social relationship subject in compulsory social studies. The curriculum also included the optional II geography in class 11 and 12 similarly, 5 credit hour and 160 working hour.

Table 16: *Secondary Education of Geography subject (Class 11-12)*

S.N.	Units	Working hours	Percentage (%)
1	Introduction to Geography	5	3.1
2	Physical Geography	60	37.5
3	Human Geography	25	15.6
4	Geography of Nepal	30	18.8
5	Practical Geography	40	25
Total		160	100

CDC, 2076

Table 16 Show the optional Geography subject of secondary education level class 11 and 12 The curriculum is included the optional II geography in class 11 and 12 similarly, 5 credit hour and 160 working. Due to the Government policy of Nepal student of geography subject are gradually decreasing. These days, Nominal students read this subject in Nepal.

Enrolment of Geography Student in School Education

National Curriculum Framework: The national curriculum framework updated the school-level curriculum based on the federal structure of the country in 2019. The recommendations of the national curriculum framework made social studies and lifeskill education a mandatory subject for Grade 11 and 12. These subjects have also addressed some of the geographic topics under geography and social relationship in the curriculum. Table 2 shows the student enrolment in geography in grades 11 and 12. The result indicates that 95 students majoring in geography in 2076/77 B. S. and it was 131 2072/73 B. S. in Nepal. This figure revealed that 3 percent of students decreased annually within five years.

The Higher Secondary Education Board (HSEB) was established in 1989 under the Higher Secondary Education Act and launched the curriculum of class 11 and 12. Higher Secondary level examination board and Secondary level education board is merged in National Examinations Board according to the Education Act (8th amendment) of 2073 B.S. Geography subject implemented the class 11 (Geo. ed.205) and 12 (Geo. Ed. 206) as an optional subject of full marks 100 (practical 25 and theoretical 75). The enrolment of the students in higher secondary education is presented in table 17.

Table 17. Enrollments of class 11 and 12

S. N.	Grade	2072/ 73	2073/74	2074/75	2075/76	2076/77	2077/78
1	11	68	58	52	49	46	-
2	12	63	67	58	52	49	29

Source : GoN, 2022

Table 17 shows the number of students of the higher secondary level of geography subject. The data is the total student of geography in Nepal. Nominal student read the geography in higher secondary level. Similarly, number of student has gradually decreasing year by year of this subject. In academic year 2072/73, only 68 and 63 students were enrolled in grade 11 and 12 respectively. But these students gradually decreasing and reach to 46 and 49 respectively class 11 and 12 in academic years 2076/77. The miserable number of the geography because the student gradually decreasing day by day.

In the past time lot of student read this subject because it is a compulsory subject. These days it is an elective subject and the students get the opportunity of the other choice subject. Other side the Government does not provide the good job market. For example Teachers Service Commission was not advertisement of Geography subject for secondary level teacher in 2078. Similarly, we have set the curriculum of GIS at the university level and computer education from the basic level. Combining this with computer education would have given GIS basic subjects from the basic level if the interest in geography would have increased and then the number of students studying this subject electively would have increased. In this concern, Janwali et al. (2015) suggested that the school-level geography curriculum be explored equally as the location. Their institutional research findings indicate a strong need for making geography a compulsory subject at the school level. It is needed to require preparing the marketable curriculum that creates jobs, management of effective teaching with monitoring and evaluation, and refresher training for teachers to enhance geography education as a discipline. Other factors competency in contents, technical terminology, methods, languages, and government policies are equally essential to the continuity of the curriculum (Graves, 1996; Andrew, 1996; Rawling, 1996).

Thus, Graves (1996) suggests that the geography curriculum must result from the interaction of the curriculum process should be outlined:

1. The general objectives to be used in the geography content (concepts, principles, and skills, not facts) essential to be certain in the light of the public education aims decided for the national education system. Certainly, these objectives will be attained according to the intellectual development of the students at different levels of the school.

2. To large level, what is achievable at any level is somewhat that teachers learn from their evaluation of the development made by their learners through psychological knowledge of mental development.

3. The teaching approaches used; need to be in coherence with the objectives set. Thus if one of the objectives is to develop the ability to make decisions in urban planning, there is no point in getting pupils to learn a ready-made solution to the problem. Thus teaching plans depend on what objectives is set, and equally, teaching methods that are attractive to teachers and students certainly affect the type of objectives.

4. The selection of content is dependent on the general objectives aimed. Then, only those parts of the discipline that are supposed to fulfill these general objectives will be selected, and those elements of the content will become the specific objectives, lessons or teaching units that form the basis of the teachers. Thus, ultimately much depends on what is seeing as the aims of education and within these the general objectives of geographical education. The effect will considerably reduce the content of what is teach, to enable a deepening of understanding and an increased capacity to use tools of the geographer.

IV. Conclusion

Geography is an important discipline and mother science for all the educational discipline. Direct and indirect geography education was taught in Nepal. The formally Geography subject was included in Nepal in 1834. At that time the subject was compulsory subject and lot of students was taught. After that time, this subject was organized as an optional/ elective subject. At present time geography subject is organized as elective subject from school level to high education level. Owing to that the trend of students' enrollment in this subject is decreasing annually that must be realized as educational issues by the concerned stakeholders. Hence, geography subject matter should be included the local level, province and federal geographical units according to geographical restructure of nation. It is needed to require preparing the marketable curriculum that creates jobs, management of effective teaching with monitoring and evaluation, and refresher training for teachers to enhance geography education as a discipline.

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